

Information, Special Relativity and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part II

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The Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ in the rest frame is $A = -\text{mot}$ ($c=1$) which has a unique value for any x for a fixed t . In other words, any x point at the same t gives the same A value. This suggests an equal probability for each x over the range $-\infty$ to ∞ .

One may perform a Lorentz transformation for a given frame moving with constant velocity $-v$, and each x, t point will transfer into a different x', t' point, i.e. the times t' in the moving frame are no longer the same. Thus, all x points are equal in the rest frame, but transform to different x' at different t' s so we suggested in Part I that one cannot conclude that there is a uniform distribution in x' over $-\infty$ to ∞ .

If one considers a single $x=0, t$ in the rest frame, it becomes a specific x', t' in the moving frame. $A = -Et + px$ has the same value in the rest and moving frame for this x, t and its corresponding x', t' . We have noted previously, that one has degenerate A values for $x' + n\hbar/p$ and $t' + n\hbar/E$, where n is an integer. These new x_1', t_1' values must map back to an x_1, t_1 in the rest frame because A is unique in the rest frame for a given t . In other words, this set of new $x_1(n)', t_1(n)'$ values are a subset of the set of x, t in the rest frame. As a result, we ask: Why should one even consider these extra pieces $n\hbar/p$ and $n\hbar/E$? Why should these be associated with time and space resolution, i.e. free particle quantum mechanics? We argue that they are relevant because in the rest frame one also has $-Et + px$. Even though this is of the form $-\text{mot}$ this is a little misleading because $p \rightarrow 0$ for $x \rightarrow \infty$ would yield a constant which cancels with $-Et$ using $t = 1/m_0$. In other words, the \hbar/p and \hbar/E degeneracies or resolutions already exist in the rest frame we argue, but one can only have $n=1$ because one cannot go beyond ∞ for x . This resolution is the basis of free particle quantum mechanics, we suggest.

Lorentz Invariant $A = -Et + px$

$A = -Et + px$ ((1)) is a Lorentz invariant. If one considers the rest frame with $p=0$, one would write:

$$A = -m_0 c^2 t \quad ((2))$$

((2)) has the same value for any x as long as t is a given value. At any t , any x point is as good as another. Another way to phrase this is that one has a uniform x probability distribution over all x . Furthermore, A is unique for a given t .

If one considers the rest frame trajectory, i.e. t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots , then A changes according to ((2)) along this trajectory.

We note that one may apply a Lorentz transformation for a given frame moving with constant $-v$ for each x, t point. The result is a set of x', t' such that t' values are all different. Thus, one cannot conclude, we suggest, that one has a uniform x distribution over all x as seen in the moving frame. We argued this in Part I.

Degeneracy of A

If one considers a given $x=0$, t in the rest frame, it transforms to a unique x',t' as seen in the moving such that:

$$A = -Et' + px' = -m_0 t \quad ((2))$$

(The same consideration applies to other x,t points from the rest frame.)

In previous notes, we have argued that for:

$$x' + n \cdot \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t' + n \cdot \hbar/E \quad ((3))$$

A remains unchanged. This is no surprise because it is known that all x,t points in the rest frame map to x',t' points in the moving frame, so the points ((3)) should be a subset of these x,t points. This begs the question: Why should one consider ((3)) in the first place? We have argued previously that \hbar/p and \hbar/E represent x and t resolutions, but why should this be the case if they are simply a subset of the x,t points in the rest frame? It may seem that this resolution is introduced a priori (or forced) in ((3)). We argue that this is not the case by considering the rest frame. At first, one may consider:

$$A = -m_0 t, \text{ but really one has } A = -m_0 t + p x \text{ where } p \rightarrow 0 \text{ and } x \rightarrow \text{infinite} \quad ((4))$$

Using the viewpoint of ((4)), a $p=0$ really means that one requires an infinite x to create a finite value 1 which cancels with $t=1/m_0$. The infinite x value means that there is an infinite x range for $p=0$ (consistent with quantum mechanics) and a $1/m_0$ time resolution for m_0 (also consistent with quantum mechanics).

We argue that the idea of time and x resolution linked to $1/E$ and $1/p$ already exist in the rest frame, (We suggested this in Part I, but try to clarify here.) As a result, ((3)) should represent time and spatial resolutions as seen in the moving frame. For p not zero, one sees that the x resolution becomes sharper, i.e. x is within $1/p$ and not within infinite. This explains why one uses $n \cdot \hbar/p$ where n is an integer. One is creating repeated resolution units.

$-Et' + px'$ and $t' \rightarrow t' + \delta_1$, $x' \rightarrow x' + \delta_2$

We consider the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ and ask: What values of δ_1 and δ_2 leave A invariant. A solution is:

$$\delta_1 = \text{constant}/E \quad \delta_2 = \text{constant}/p \quad ((5))$$

The question we then ask is: Why can one not have an infinite set of constants instead of the one constant used in ((3)). It is the one constant used in ((3)), namely \hbar , which leads to the use of the integer n to indicate repeated resolution units. This in turn leads to the quantum mechanical viewpoint, i.e. there is periodicity in quantum mechanics. If there are infinite constant values, then one does not have discrete jumps linked to the integer n and hence no quantum mechanics. To answer this question, we go back to the previous section and note that in the rest frame, there is one constant because $p \rightarrow 0$ and $x \rightarrow \infty$ such that $px \rightarrow \text{constant}$. Thus, it is the probabilistic view point with resolutions in the rest frame which seems to govern the use of ((3)) as opposed to using any constant in ((5)).

As an example, we consider $x=0$, t in the rest frame, such that $x'=gvt$ and $t'=gt$ where $g=1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. We use the inverse Lorentz transformation to transform x',t' with the extra resolution pieces ((3)) to show that one does get back t which is required for the unique A value.

$$\begin{aligned} |g -vg| |vgt +n/p| &= |t(1-v) + gn (1/p-v/E)| \quad ((6)) \\ |-vg g| |gt+n/E| &= |t+ gn(-v/p+1/E)| \end{aligned}$$

Here $-v/p+1/E = 0$ for $c=1$ so one has t in the rest frame as required.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the main point we present is that $A = -Et'+px'$ as seen in a moving frame has degenerate A values for $x'+n*\hbar/p$ and $t'+n*\hbar/E$. The point, however, is that in the rest frame $A = -mot$ and so any x,t yields the same A value. Thus, all x points have equal probability. The set $x'+n*\hbar/p$ and $t'+n*\hbar/E$ for a given x',t' are simply a subset of these x,t points Lorentz transformed using v . We suggest one has to be cautious about suggesting that \hbar/p and \hbar/E represent spatial and temporal resolutions. We argue, however, that they do because in the rest frame, one really has $A = -mot + px$ for $p > 0$, $x \rightarrow \infty$. Then $t \sim 1/mo$. Thus, the time and space resolutions actually exist in the rest frame, except the spatial one is $x \rightarrow \infty$. For p not zero, this spatial resolution becomes smaller. Thus, the idea of probability (uniform probability distributions over x) originates in the rest frame for special relativity and then carries over into the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$.